

TECHNOLOGY FOR ORGANIZING WRESTLING CLASSES WITH PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

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Annotation: The article substantiates the need to involve young people with disabilities in active physical education and sports in order to increase the level of their physical activity. This process is accompanied by significant changes in pedagogical theory and practice of educational work, which makes it possible to develop a methodology for conducting training sessions in kurash wrestling in sports and recreation groups with a sports focus.

Key words: kurash wrestling, physical activity, disabled people, modular block planning, sports and recreation groups.

Introduction. In modern society, the pace of social changes associated with population mobility, disability, including obtaining education and playing sports has increased sharply [2, 4].

These processes actualize the need to develop issues of physical and psychological preparation, socialization and adaptation of the individual to life in a cultural environment, in particular, in solving the problems of adaptation of disabled people to the current educational process, to living conditions in the new socio-cultural environment of national states [1, 3, 5]. This explains the need to involve disabled people in active physical education and sports in order to increase the level of their motor and communicative activity [6, 8, 9].

Para-sports refers to mass forms of organizing physical exercise, since the life of a disabled person is not only a period of mastering knowledge and familiarization with world socio-cultural values, but also, above all, a time of forming one's own

criteria for a personal healthy lifestyle and increasing physical activity, improving health and development of motor abilities [7, 10, 11].

The purpose of parasports is to strengthen the health of the people and people with disabilities, cultivate positive moral qualities, organize a healthy lifestyle and solve various social problems. Parasport has a largely health-improving effect [12, 13]. Physical training is a powerful means of restoring mental and physical strength, helping to cope with the problems of adaptation to new living conditions and educational activities [14, 15, 16]. According to scientists, further development of ideas for increasing the efficiency of the process of physical education of disabled people is possible on the basis of involving them in systematic sports, including kurash wrestling, the use of sports training technology, and physical education and recreational activities [17, 19, 22].

It is known that kurash wrestling is a natural, nature-conditioned human need for martial arts. Kurash wrestling is popular in many countries of the world and interest in this type of martial arts is growing [18, 20, 21].

Kurash wrestling is practiced by people of different age groups with disabilities. The main goal of kurash wrestling is the development of a harmoniously developed personality; the basis of kurash wrestling is still relevant today.

The interest of young people with disabilities in oriental martial arts is due to the novelty and philosophical ideas preached by the culture of the East; this is a kind of dialogue between cultures and civilizations. The depth of the philosophical ideas underlying kurash wrestling, the nobility of the goal set - the education of a harmoniously developed personality, worthy behavior - all this contributed to the recognition and popularity of kurash wrestling.

Kurash wrestling classes help solve problems that are relevant for young people with disabilities: moral education, harmonious physical development, mastery of motor skills [23, 24, 25]. Taking into account the philosophical ideas, moral and ethical principles, means and methods used for physical and moral improvement in kurash wrestling, it can be effectively used in organizing physical

education among young people with disabilities and contribute to the development of universal values of physical culture. The generally accepted terminology of kurash wrestling will contribute to the development of communication skills among people with disabilities.

The organization of physical education among young people with disabilities using accessible means and methods of sports training, as well as rating assessment of physical education and sports activities have a great prospect for optimizing the educational process of physical education [27, 28].

It is emphasized that it is especially important to increase the effectiveness of physical education to recognize the priority of training as the leading and most effective way to transform physical potential among disabled people.

The basis of the content of physical education training should be considered:

- traditional means and methods of physical education (complexes of general developmental exercises, their combinations and connections, basic types of movements, their complicated variants, game tasks and games);
- modern innovative means and methods of physical education (circuit training, mastering basic kurash wrestling techniques);
- components of sports training technology (basic developmental blocks based on retracting, stabilizing, basic technical, restorative modules).

However, attracting young people with disabilities to systematic training in kurash wrestling requires a change in the methods and means of the training process, a more in-depth individual approach based on a comprehensive study of the body's abilities and capabilities.

When organizing kurash wrestling classes, planning plays a special role with disabled people, in which it is important to take into account the following factors:

- state of health and physical fitness, as well as individual characteristics of the course of adaptation processes (psychophysiological, social);
- the presence of a certain limited barrier associated with different initial levels of proficiency in motor activity;

- features of disability groups, opportunities in matters of physical education [26, 29].

In achieving sustainable adaptation, the factor of the speed of mobilization of physiological reserves and adaptive mechanisms plays an important role. Therefore, the slower the increase in physical activity, the easier it is for the body to adapt to it. This is precisely what needs to be taken into account when choosing a physical education regime, since with a sharp change in the duration or intensity of physical activity, the development of maladaptation is possible. It is also important in the process of training to mobilize and use physiological reserves for maximum adaptation to physical loads, as well as to expand the body's reserve capabilities to increase its resistance to the effects of various stress factors not only during classes, training and competitions, but also to stress factors Everyday life. It is known that the physiological mechanisms of adaptation to the effects of various extreme (stressful) factors on humans are similar to each other.

Conclusions. The design of the macrocycle for training students - kurash wrestlers is carried out taking into account the priority factors for a particular module that determine its structure and content. The design of the structure and especially the content of the module should be based on a clear understanding of the place and role of this module in the macrocycle, thereby ensuring consistent continuity of tasks solved throughout the year in the development of sportsmanship.

When compiling a macrocycle of training sessions in a sports and recreational group, a conjugate method of training and development is used.

Kurash wrestling training is a pedagogical process aimed at developing knowledge, skills and abilities with the continuous implementation of tasks of comprehensive physical development. Modeling the training process for youth with disabilities in a modular-block version will have a positive impact on physical development and improvement of motor qualities; the use of block-modular planning is effective in training disabled athletes at various stages of training.

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Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості= Голопристанский районный центр занятости.

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